

Decision to Invest Using Markowitz Model on LQ 45 Index Companies for the Period 2015 – 2019

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to find viable shares in the optimal portfolio as well as the proportion of funds from each of these stocks formed with the Markowitz Model. This research method uses literature research design. Data collection techniques are documentation. While the analysis of research data is started with the processing and preparation of data until interpreting the meaning of data. The population in this study was all companies listed in the LQ Index 45 as of December 31, 2019. While the sample is Companies that never exited the LQ 45 Index during the period 2015-2019. The results of this study showed that the shares of LQ Index 45 companies in the period 2015 – 2019 which formed an optimal portfolio based on the Markowitz model of 150 stock portfolios. From the overall weighting obtained the results of a portfolio of shares 40% ADRO & 60% BBCA, 50% ADRO & 50% BBCA and 60% ADRO & 40% BBCA are optimal portfolios for aggressive investor profiles, furthermore 40% BBCA stock portfolio & 60% UNVR, 50% AKRA & 50% BBCA, 60% BBCA & 40% GGRM are optimal portfolios for conservative investor profiles. While the stock portfolio of 40% BBCA & 60% BBTN, 50% BBCA & 50% BBTN and 60% BBCA & 40% BBTN is the optimal portfolio for the profile of moderate investors.

Keywords: Optimal portfolio, Markowitz Model

I. Introduction

Capital markets are challenged through the era of the digital economy to become more modern. With that condition, the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) together with the Indonesian Securities Guarantee Clearing (KPEI) and the Indonesian Central Securities Depository (KSEI) continue to strive to provide the best service. These efforts are made to improve infrastructure and expand the reach of capital markets throughout Indonesia. In order to answer business challenges, the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) launched a new trading system called Jakarta Automated Trading Systems Next Generation (JATS NextG) which has a capacity of 1 million orders and 500 thousand transactions per day and is able to handle multi products in a single platform (Indonesia, 2018). The Application of Jakarta Automated Trading Systems Next Generation (JATS NextG) is able to make public access to invest in the capital market easier and faster. Therefore, it requires sufficient knowledge, experience and business instincts to analyze which shares to buy, which shares to sell and which shares remain owned.

In fact, investing in stocks, returns and risk are two things that can not be separated. A high return will contain a high risk as well. Conversely, a low risk will have a low return as well. Therefore, investors are required to be able to make the right decisions in investing, so as to minimize risk. The right decision that can be used by investors in reducing the risk of investing is by diversifying. Diversification can be done by investing in different types of stocks, so as to form a portfolio (Sharpe, Alexander and Bailey, 2005). The purpose of forming a stock portfolio is to obtain maximum return expectations with a minimum level of risk (Hartono, 2015).

The Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) publishes stock indexes containing companies with certain criteria to overcome the difficulties experienced by investors. One of the indices is the LQ 45 Index, the stock contained in the LQ 45 Index is a liquid stock, high market capitalization, has good growth prospects, has a high frequency of trading and has a fairly good financial condition (Indonesia, 2015). Thus, when viewed from the risk side of the LQ45 stock group, it has the lowest risk compared to other stocks. The following in table 1 are presented the return of shares of companies listed in the LQ Index 45 Period 2015 – 2019 as follows :

Table 1. Return of Company Shares listed in the LQ 45 Index Period 2015–2019

No	Stock Code	Return				
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	ADRO	-0,505	2,291	0,097	-0,347	2,251
2	AKRA	0,742	-0,164	0,058	-0,324	-0,079
3	ASII	-0,192	0,379	0,003	-0,009	-0,158
4	BBCA	0,013	0,165	0,413	0,187	0,286
5	BBNI	-0,182	0,107	0,792	-0,111	-0,108
6	BBRI	-0,019	0,022	-0,688	0,005	0,202
7	BBTN	0,075	0,344	1,052	-0,289	-0,165
8	BMRI	-0,142	0,251	-0,309	-0,078	0,041
9	BSDE	-0,003	-0,025	-0,031	-0,262	0,000
10	GGRM	-0,094	0,162	0,311	-0,002	-0,366
11	ICBP	0,029	-0,364	0,038	0,174	0,067
12	INCO	-0,549	0,725	0,025	0,128	0,117
13	INDF	-0,233	0,531	-0,038	-0,023	0,064
14	INTP	-0,107	-0,310	0,425	-0,159	0,031
15	JSMR	-0,259	-0,173	0,481	-0,331	0,209
16	KLBF	-0,279	0,148	0,116	-0,101	0,066
17	LPPF	0,173	-0,141	-0,339	-0,440	-0,248
18	MNCN	-0,270	-0,054	-0,268	-0,463	1,362
19	PGAS	-0,543	-0,016	-0,352	0,211	0,024
20	PTBA	-0,651	1,762	-0,803	0,748	-0,381
21	PTPP	0,084	-0,017	-0,307	-0,316	-0,122
22	SCMA	-0,114	-0,097	-0,114	-0,246	-0,246
23	SMGR	-0,296	-0,195	0,079	0,162	0,043
24	TLKM	0,084	0,282	0,116	-0,155	0,059
25	UNTR	-0,023	0,254	0,666	-0,227	-0,213
26	UNVR	0,146	0,049	0,441	-0,188	-0,075
27	WIKA	-0,283	-0,106	-0,343	0,068	0,202
28	WSKT	0,136	0,527	-0,133	-0,240	-0,116

Source : Processed Data, 2020

Based on table 1 above, it can be seen that although the shares of companies listed in the LQ 45 Index are 45 companies that have high liquidity and high market capitalization and are known as blue chip stock groups but are inseparable from uncertainty about the level of return that investors will receive. It can be seen in table 1 that the return of shares of sampled companies from the LQ 45 Index during the period 2015-2019 fluctuates. The highest share return was in PT Adaro Energy, Tbk (ADRO) in 2016 at 2.291 while the lowest return on shares was pt Bukit Asam (Persero), Tbk (PTBA) in 2017 of -0.803.

Furthermore, the return of shares in 2019 from each company listed in index LQ 45 decreased. This indicates that there is an element of risk in such investments Another problem that is often faced by investors is when they have to choose stocks that will be formed into portfolios so that in the end the investor makes the wrong portfolio decision to choose then this has an impact on the return that will be received by the investor. Therefore, a way to analyze stock selection and optimal portfolio determination is needed.

(Hartono, 2015) stated that the optimal portfolio is a portfolio formed with the best return on expectations and risks. Optimal portfolio formation can be done by means of the Markowitz Model. Markowitz's mean-variance method indicates that securities with a correlation less than +1 lower portfolio risk. The more securities formed into a portfolio, the less portfolio risk. Diversification will eliminate the effects of the variant, but the covariant effect still remains. A well-diversified portfolio consisting of many stocks, as well as the effects of covariance will be more important than the effect of the variants of each share itself.

Therefore, this research uses the Markowitz Model in portfolio formation, where stock selection and optimal portfolio determination are carried out by collecting historical data on individual shares that are used as inputs and analyzed for output in the form of a combination of several stocks that can describe the performance of each portfolio and can determine whether the portfolio is classified as an optimal portfolio or vice versa.

This research was inspired by research conducted by (Yunita, 2018) with the title Markowitz Model in The Establishment of Optimal Portfolio (Case Study on Jakarta Islamic Index). The results showed that there are 10 stocks included in the optimal portfolio, namely AKRA (3.4%), ADRO (3.3%), ICBP (4.7%), INCO (2.6%), MYRX (13.6%), PTPP (4.9%), PWON (11.3%), TPIA (1%), UNTR (15.7%) and UNVR (39.5%). The average portfolio return rate is 1.22 % and portfolio risk is 0.0312, the risk is below the risk of each individual stock forming the optimal portfolio. Furthermore, research conducted by (Setyawati and Sudiarta, 2019) with the results of the study showed from fourteen stock samples, selected seven stocks that managed to be optimal portfolio candidates from the Markowitz model. Seven shares with a proportion of fund allocation, namely ADRO shares (0.55%), ASII (0.15%), GGRM (17.61%), ICBP (9.46%), MEDC (5,275), UNVR (41.11%), and UNTR (25.86%), resulting in an expected return of 3.2% and with a risk rate of 3.3%. The difference between this research and the research conducted by (Yunita, 2018) and (Setyawati and Sudiarta, 2019) is this research using all companies listed in Index LQ 45 with the period 2015–2019.

II. Literature Review

1. Capital Market

Companies that need funds can sell their securities in the capital market. Capital Market can be said to be an abstract market, because what is traded is a long-term fund that is a fund that is related to investing for more than a year (Lubis, 2008).

2. Return

Return is the result of investment. Return can be in the form of realization return that has occurred or return expectations that have not occurred but are expected to occur in the future (Hartono, 2015).

1. Realized Return or R_i

Return realization is calculated based on historical data, this return is important because it is used as one of the performance meters of the company. Return realization is important because it is used as one of the performance measurement tools of the company.

2. Expected Return or $E(R_i)$

Expected Return is a return that is expected to be obtained by investors in the future. In contrast to the return of realization that has occurred, the return of expectations has not occurred (Hartono, 2015).

3. Risk

Risk is often associated with deviations or deviations from outcomes received with those expected. In the investment concept, in general the risk can be classified into 2 i.e. (Hartono, 2015):

1. Systematic risk, is a macro risk because it is related to changes that occur in the market as a whole and can result in variability of investment returns.
2. Unsystematic risk is a risk associated with changing the risk of certain micro-condition of a particular company so that it will specifically affect the return on investment of the company.

To calculate risk, the widely used method is standard deviation that measures absolute deviation of values that have occurred with the expected value (Hartono, 2015).

4. Investor Type Based on Risk Profile

An investor's risk profile describes his level of tolerance for risk, or the extent to which he or she can bear the risk. This risk profile is usually influenced by a variety of factors such as age, environment and understanding of investment (M. Investasi, 2020).

In the risk profile itself, there are three types of investors that have been grouped, namely (Ajarinvestasi, 2018):

1. Conservative

Conservative investors are the type of investors who have a low tolerance for investment. Or in other words, tend to choose a stable type of investment, low risk or even no risk at all. Usually those who fall into the conservative category are novice investors who are just interested in investing. Conservative types of investors are usually also less problematic if the return on investment obtained is small, provided that the initial capital they invest is not lost. The bottom line is 'it doesn't matter a little – a little bit longer – long to be a hill, as long as the risk is low and the initial capital doesn't disappear'. For conservative-type investors, mutual funds that are suitable for investment are money market mutual funds because money market mutual funds have a fairly low level of risk, and are suitable for investors who invest with short-term goals. Investors will still get a return, and do not have to worry about price fluctuations in the capital market.

2. Moderate

For moderate-type investors, it can still tolerate risks in investing. But not for considerable risk and still remain careful in choosing safe investment instruments. Fluctuations in the capital market when investing have begun to be understood in this type of investor. Fixed income mutual funds and mixed mutual funds can be one example of investments suitable for moderate-type investors.

3. Aggressive

This type of aggressive investor is the type of investor who is accustomed to fluctuations in capital market prices, even against extreme fluctuations. This type of investor is also not afraid to put capital in high-risk investment instruments such as stock mutual funds.

But of course, such as the basic principles of mutual fund investment are Low Risk – Low Return, and High Risk – High Return. Investment in high-risk instruments can also provide an opportunity to get a drastically soaring return.

5. Portfolio

Portfolios are investments in various types of securities, stocks, bonds, money markets and derivative products. As a combination of different types of securities with different investment weight compositions each type of securities are in one portfolio package (Samsul, 2015). A rational investor will invest by diversifying to form a portfolio so as to minimize risk without having to reduce the expected return.

6. Efficient Portfolio and Optimal Portfolio

Efficient portfolios are good portfolios but not the best. An efficient portfolio can be defined as a portfolio that provides the greatest return expectations with certain risks or provides the smallest risk with a certain expectation return (Hartono, 2015). Rational investors will choose efficient portfolios because they are portfolios formed by optimizing one of two dimensions, namely return expectations or portfolio risk.

Optimal portfolio is a portfolio with the best combination of return expectations and risks (Hartono, 2015). An optimal portfolio is also an efficient portfolio, but an efficient portfolio is not necessarily an optimal portfolio.

7. Optimal Portfolio Based on the Markowitz Model

Optimal portfolio is a portfolio chosen by investors from the many options contained in efficient portfolios. The optimal portfolio can be determined using the Markowitz Model (Hartono, 2015). By (Tandelilin, 2010) diversification of assets naively as well as with the Markowitz model proved able to provide benefits to investors in the form of portfolio risk reduction. The downside of diversification naively is that investors do not take advantage of available information such as the company's industry characteristics and expected return rate, so the diversification carried out is not yet optimal. Markowitz's approach can overcome the shortcomings of naive diversification, because by using the Markowitz model, investors can use all the information as a basic reference for optimal portfolio formation. (Hartono, 2015) said that the Markowitz Model uses assumptions such as time spent on only 1 period, absence of transaction fees, investors only based on portfolio expectations and risks, and absence of risk-free deposits and guarantees.

III. Methodology

1. Types of Research

This research is a descriptive research that is research conducted to find out the independent variables either one variable or more (independent) to make comparisons or connect with other variables. The approach taken in this research is by quantitative approach, because the main data used in this research is in the form of numbers.

2. Population and Sample

The population in this study was all companies registered in LQ 45 from 2015–2019 period of 68 population. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is the sampling of data based on certain criteria. The criteria of purposive sampling are listed companies and never exit the LQ 45 Index from the period 2015–2019. From these criteria obtained 28 companies listed in the LQ 45 Index that will be sampled in this study. The companies sampled in this study were as follows: ADRO, AKRA, ASII, BBKA, BBNI, BBRI, BBTN, BMRI, BSDE, GGRM, ICBP, INCO, INDF, INTP, JSMR, KLBF, LPPF, MNCN, PGAS, PTBA, SCMA, SMGR, TLKM, UNTR, UNVR, WIKA, and WSKT.

3. Variable and Measurement

The variables and measurements used in this study are as follows:

- a. The closing share price of each sample company

The closing share price of each sampled company is taken from the closing price of each period, namely during the period 2015-2019 from the duniainvestasi.com (D. Investasi, 2020).

- b. Return each sample company's shares with a formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$R_{i,t} = \frac{(P_{it} - P_{it-1})}{P_{it-1}} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Description :

- Rit = Return on i shares in t period
- Pit = Share price i in t period
- Pit-1 = Share price i in the period t-1

- c. Expected return of each sample company's shares with formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$E(R_i) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n R_{it}}{n} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Description :

- E(R_i) = Expected Return on i shares
- Rit = Return on i shares in t period
- n = Number of observation periods

- d. Risk of each sample company's shares with standard deviation calculation using formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n [R_{it} - E(R_i)]^2}{n}} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Description :

- SD = Standard deviation
- R_{it} = Return on i shares in t period
- E(R_i) = Expected Return on i shares
- n = Number of observation periods

- e. Covariance between stocks to know the tendency between stocks to move simultaneously, namely using a formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$\sigma_{RA, RB} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [(R_{Ai} - E(R_a)) \cdot (R_{Bi} - E(R_b))]}{n} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Description :

- σ_{RA, RB} = Covariance return between A and B shares
- R_{Ai} = Return on A shares in t period

- R_{Bi} = Return on B shares in t period
- $E(R_A)$ = Expected Return on A shares
- $E(R_B)$ = Expected Return on B shares
- n = Number of observation periods

f. Correlation coefficients between stocks to measure how big the relationship between stocks is, i.e. using a formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$r_{AB} = \rho_{AB} = \frac{\text{Cov}(R_A, R_B)}{\sigma_A \sigma_B} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Description :

- r_{AB} = Correlation coefficient of return on stocks A and B
- $\text{Cov}(R_A R_B)$ = Covariant value of shares
- σ_A = Standard deviation of A stocks
- σ_B = Standard deviation of B stocks

g. Expected return of the existing portfolio, i.e. using the formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$E(R_p) = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i E(R_i) \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Description :

- $E(R_p)$ = Expected Return on portfolio
- $E(R_i)$ = Expected Return on i shares
- W_i = Portion of i shares against all shares in portfolio
- n = Number of shares in the portfolio

h. Portfolio risk with standard deviation calculation combined with covariant value to calculate the tendency of stock movement simultaneously, i.e. using formula (Hartono, 2015):

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n W_i W_j \sigma_{ij}} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Description :

- σ_p = Standard deviation of portfolio
- σ_{ij} = Covariance between shares i and j
- W_i = Weighting or portion of funds invested in shares i
- W_j = Weighting or portion of funds invested in shares j
- $\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n$ = Double sum mark
- n = Number of shares in the portfolio

i. The ninth stage is the calculation of optimal weight or proportion with solver program. The purpose of solver program is to calculate how much weighting or optimal proportion of funds of each share in each portfolio.

j. Expected Return and optimal portfolio deviation standards, i.e. using formulas (Hartono, 2015):

$$\sigma_p = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i \sigma_i^2 + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n W_i W_j \sigma_{ij} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

Description :

- σ_p = Standard deviation of portfolio
- W_i = Weighting or portion of funds invested in shares i
- $\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n$ = Double sum mark
- n = Number of shares in the portfolio

4. Data Collection Techniques

The data collection techniques used in this research are by documentation. This technique is carried out by looking at secondary data that has been provided by the Indonesia Stock Exchange including records, report reports, and form forms in accordance with the research.

5. Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis is performed with the help of Microsoft Excel. The stages of sequential data analysis can be described as follows :

1. Collecting closing price data of each share
2. Calculate the return of each sample company's shares
3. Calculate the expected return of each sample company's shares
4. Calculate the risk of each sample company's shares
5. Calculate Covariance between stocks in order to know the tendency between stocks to move simultaneously
6. Calculating correlation coefficients between stocks to measure how big the relationship between stocks is
7. Calculate expected return of a formed portfolio
8. Calculate portfolio risk by calculating standard deviation combined with covariant value to calculate the tendency of stock movement simultaneously
9. Calculate the optimal weight or proportion
10. Calculate expected Return and standard of optimal portfolio deviation

Determine the optimal portfolio for investors with the aggressive, conservative and moderate profile of some already formed porfotolio with certain returns and risks.

IV. Results

Calculation of Stock Return, Expected Return and Standard Deviation

After the stock return calculation, the next step in this research is to calculate the expected return of shares for each sample of the company. The risk is directly proportional to the Return which means that the higher the rate of return expected by the investor, the higher the risk that will be borne by the investor. In this study, the expected return used is the expectation of return that has a positive value that will be used as an optimal portfolio candidate. The following are presented stock returns, expected returns to be optimal portfolio candidates as well as standard deviations in companies listed in the LQ Index 45 period 2015-2019 as follows :

Table 2. Stock Return, Expected Return and Standard Deviation of Companies listed in the LQ Index 45 Period 2015-2019

Sort Number	Stock Code	ΣR_i	E(Ri)	E(Ri) %	σ	σ (%)
1	ADRO	3,788	0,758	75,8	2,799	279,9
2	AKRA	0,232	0,046	4,6	0,825	82,5
3	ASII	0,023	0,005	0,5	0,439	43,9
4	BBCA	1,064	0,213	21,3	0,543	54,3
5	BBNI	0,498	0,100	10,0	1,293	129,3
6	BBTN	1,016	0,203	20,3	2,201	220,1
7	GGRM	0,011	0,002	0,2	0,512	51,2
8	INCO	0,445	0,089	8,9	0,734	73,4
9	INDF	0,301	0,060	6,0	0,570	57,0
10	MNCN	0,308	0,062	6,2	1,284	128,4
11	PTBA	0,675	0,135	13,5	14,945	1494,5
12	TLKM	0,384	0,077	7,7	0,313	31,3
13	UNTR	0,456	0,091	9,1	0,751	75,1
14	UNVR	0,372	0,074	7,4	0,481	48,1
15	WSKT	0,174	0,035	3,5	0,616	61,6

Source : Processed Data, 2020

Based on Table 2 it can be known that there are 15 companies that are expected to return positive value. The highest expected return was pt Adaro Energy, Tbk (ADRO) at 0.758 (75.8%) while companies that have low expected returns are located in the company PT Gudang Garam, Tbk (GGRM) of 0.002 (0.2%). Furthermore, the company with the

largest risk value is PT Bukit Asam, Tbk (PTBA) which is 14,945 (1,494.5 %) while the company with the lowest risk value is PT Telekomunikasi Indonesia, Tbk (TLKM) of 0.313 (31.3%).

Calculating Stock Portfolio Combinations

Furthermore, this research calculates the combination of stock portfolio consisting of 2 shares per portfolio, so that there will be many possibilities for stocks to be formed. In calculating stock portfolio combinations can use equation

$$(r, n) = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$$

formulas , the following results will be obtained, namely :

$$(2, 15) = \frac{15!}{2!(15-2)!} = 105$$

Based on the calculation according to the number of sample shares (15 shares), 105 combinations were obtained. The following table of combinations of portfolio stocks formed is as follows:

Table 3. Stock Portfolio formed

Sort Number	Portfolio Name								
1	ADRO & AKRA	22	AKRA & MNCN	43	BBCA & INCO	64	BBTN & MNCN	85	INDF & MNCN
2	ADRO & ASII	23	AKRA & PTBA	44	BBCA & INDF	65	BBTN & PTBA	86	INDF & PTBA
3	ADRO & BBCA	24	AKRA & TLKM	45	BBCA & MNCN	66	BBTN & TLKM	87	INDF & TLKM
4	ADRO & BBNI	25	AKRA & UNTR	46	BBCA & PTBA	67	BBTN & UNTR	88	INDF & UNTR
5	ADRO & BBTN	26	AKRA & UNVR	47	BBCA & TLKM	68	BBTN & UNVR	89	INDF & UNVR
6	ADRO & GGRM	27	AKRA & WSKT	48	BBCA & UNTR	69	BBTN & WSKT	90	INDF & WSKT
7	ADRO & INCO	28	ASII & BBCA	49	BBCA & UNVR	70	GGRM & INCO	91	MNCN & PTBA
8	ADRO & INDF	29	ASII & BBNI	50	BBCA & WSKT	71	GGRM & INDF	92	MNCN & TLKM
9	ADRO & MNCN	30	ASII & BBTN	51	BBNI & BBTN	72	GGRM & MNCN	93	MNCN & UNTR
10	ADRO & PTBA	31	ASII & GGRM	52	BBNI & GGRM	73	GGRM & PTBA	94	MNCN & UNVR
11	ADRO & TLKM	32	ASII & INCO	53	BBNI & INCO	74	GGRM & TLKM	95	MNCN & WSKT
12	ADRO & UNTR	33	ASII & INDF	54	BBNI & INDF	75	GGRM & UNTR	96	PTBA & TLKM
13	ADRO & UNVR	34	ASII & MNCN	55	BBNI & MNCN	76	GGRM & UNVR	97	PTBA & UNTR
14	ADRO & WSKT	35	ASII & PTBA	56	BBNI & PTBA	77	GGRM & WSKT	98	PTBA & UNVR
15	AKRA & ASII	36	ASII & TLKM	57	BBNI & TLKM	78	INCO & INDF	99	PTBA & WSKT
16	AKRA & BBCA	37	ASII & UNTR	58	BBNI & UNTR	79	INCO & MNCN	100	TLKM & UNTR
17	AKRA & BBNI	38	ASII & UNVR	59	BBNI & UNVR	80	INCO & PTBA	101	TLKM & UNVR
18	AKRA & BBTN	39	ASII & WSKT	60	BBNI & WSKT	81	INCO & TLKM	102	TLKM & WSKT
19	AKRA & GGRM	40	BBCA & BBNI	61	BBTN & GGRM	82	INCO & UNTR	103	UNTR & UNVR
20	AKRA & INCO	41	BBCA & BBTN	62	BBTN & INCO	83	INCO & UNVR	104	UNTR & WSKT
21	AKRA & INDF	42	BBCA & GGRM	63	BBTN & INDF	84	INCO & WSKT	105	UNVR & WSKT

Source : Processed Data, 2020

Calculating Expected Return on Stock Portfolio

After obtaining shares that are included in the combination of portfolios, the next step is to include the investment weighting of the funds that have been determined, namely 40% : 60%; 50% : 50% and 60% and 40%. Furthermore, the calculation of expected return of stock portfolio with formula $E(R_p) = \alpha X_A \cdot E(R_A) + \alpha X_B \cdot E(R_B)$ are as follows:

Table 4. Return and Standard Deviation Investment Weight 40% : 60 %

No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ	No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ	No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ
1	ADRO & AKRA	0,330934	0,200945	36	ASII & TLKM	0,047984	0,082005	71	GGRM & INDF	0,037005	0,0929838
2	ADRO & ASII	0,305826	0,175837	37	ASII & UNTR	0,056590	0,073398	72	GGRM & MNCN	0,037829	0,0921601
3	ADRO & BBCA	0,430777	0,300789	38	ASII & UNVR	0,046513	0,083476	73	GGRM & PTBA	0,081909	0,0480793
4	ADRO & BBNI	0,362809	0,232820	39	ASII & WSKT	0,022707	0,107281	74	GGRM & TLKM	0,047012	0,0829767
5	ADRO & BBTN	0,424985	0,294996	40	BBCA & BBNI	0,144920	0,014931	75	GGRM & UNTR	0,055619	0,0743701
6	ADRO & GGRM	0,304368	0,174379	41	BBCA & BBTN	0,207096	0,077107	76	GGRM & UNVR	0,045541	0,0844475

7	ADRO & INCO	0,356471	0,226482	42	BBCA & GGRM	0,086479	0,043510	77	GGRM & WSKT	0,021736	0,1082530
8	ADRO & INDF	0,339167	0,209178	43	BBCA & INCO	0,138582	0,008593	78	INCO & INDF	0,071740	0,0582487
9	ADRO & MNCN	0,339990	0,210002	44	BBCA & INDF	0,121278	0,008711	79	INCO & MNCN	0,072564	0,0574250
10	ADRO & PTBA	0,384071	0,254082	45	BBCA & MNCN	0,122101	0,007887	80	INCO & PTBA	0,116644	0,0133442
11	ADRO & TLKM	0,349174	0,219185	46	BBCA & PTBA	0,166182	0,036193	81	INCO & TLKM	0,081747	0,0482416
12	ADRO & UNTR	0,357780	0,227792	47	BBCA & TLKM	0,131285	0,001296	82	INCO & UNTR	0,090354	0,0396350
13	ADRO & UNVR	0,347703	0,217714	48	BBCA & UNTR	0,139891	0,009903	83	INCO & UNVR	0,080276	0,0497124
14	ADRO & WSKT	0,323898	0,193909	49	BBCA & UNVR	0,129814	0,000175	84	INCO & WSKT	0,056471	0,0735179
15	AKRA & ASII	0,021374	0,108614	50	BBCA & WSKT	0,106009	0,023980	85	INDF & MNCN	0,061028	0,0689610
16	AKRA & BBCA	0,146326	0,016337	51	BBNI & BBTN	0,161784	0,031795	86	INDF & PTBA	0,105108	0,0248802
17	AKRA & BBNI	0,078357	0,051631	52	BBNI & GGRM	0,041167	0,088822	87	INDF & TLKM	0,070211	0,0597776
18	AKRA & BBTN	0,140534	0,010545	53	BBNI & INCO	0,093269	0,036719	88	INDF & UNTR	0,078818	0,0511710
19	AKRA & GGRM	0,019917	0,110072	54	BBNI & INDF	0,075965	0,054023	89	INDF & UNVR	0,068740	0,0612484
20	AKRA & INCO	0,072019	0,057969	55	BBNI & MNCN	0,076789	0,053200	90	INDF & WSKT	0,044935	0,0850539
21	AKRA & INDF	0,054715	0,075273	56	BBNI & PTBA	0,120870	0,009119	91	MNCN & PTBA	0,105658	0,0243311
22	AKRA & MNCN	0,055539	0,074450	57	BBNI & TLKM	0,085972	0,044016	92	MNCN & TLKM	0,070760	0,0592285
23	AKRA & PTBA	0,099620	0,030369	58	BBNI & UNTR	0,094579	0,035410	93	MNCN & UNTR	0,079367	0,0506219
24	AKRA & TLKM	0,064722	0,065266	59	BBNI & UNVR	0,084502	0,045487	94	MNCN & UNVR	0,069289	0,0606993
25	AKRA & UNTR	0,073329	0,056660	60	BBNI & WSKT	0,060696	0,069293	95	MNCN & WSKT	0,045484	0,0845048
26	AKRA & UNVR	0,063252	0,066737	61	BBTN & GGRM	0,082618	0,047371	96	PTBA & TLKM	0,100147	0,0298413
27	AKRA & WSKT	0,039446	0,090543	62	BBTN & INCO	0,134720	0,004731	97	PTBA & UNTR	0,108754	0,0212347
28	ASII & BBCA	0,129587	0,000401	63	BBTN & INDF	0,117416	0,012572	98	PTBA & UNVR	0,098677	0,0313121
29	ASII & BBNI	0,061619	0,068370	64	BBTN & MNCN	0,118240	0,011749	99	PTBA & WSKT	0,074871	0,0551176
30	ASII & BBTN	0,123795	0,006194	65	BBTN & PTBA	0,162321	0,032332	100	TLKM & UNTR	0,085489	0,0444997
31	ASII & GGRM	0,003178	0,126811	66	BBTN & TLKM	0,127423	0,002565	101	TLKM & UNVR	0,075412	0,0545770
32	ASII & INCO	0,055281	0,074708	67	BBTN & UNTR	0,136030	0,006041	102	TLKM & WSKT	0,051606	0,0783825
33	ASII & INDF	0,037977	0,092012	68	BBTN & UNVR	0,125953	0,004036	103	UNTR & UNVR	0,081149	0,0488393
34	ASII & MNCN	0,038800	0,091188	69	BBTN & WSKT	0,102147	0,027842	104	UNTR & WSKT	0,057344	0,0726448
35	ASII & PTBA	0,082881	0,047108	70	GGRM & INCO	0,054309	0,075680	105	UNVR & WSKT	0,050626	0,0793630

Source : Processed Data, 2020

From Table 4 can be described the graph of Expected Return and Risk between Individual shares with Portfolio as follows:

Source : Processed Data, 2020

Figure 1. Expected return and Risk Portfolio stock Investment Weight 40 % : 60 %

Based on Table 4 and Figure 1 it can be determined that with an investment weight of 40% : 60 % that the right stock portfolio investment for the profile of aggressive investors is in the portfolio of ADRO & BBCA shares with the highest risk level (σ) of 0.300789 with a return rate (R_i) of 0.430777. Furthermore, the conservative investor profile is in the BBCA & UNVR stock portfolio with the lowest risk level (σ) of 0.0001745 with a return rate (R_i) of 0.129814. As for the profile of moderate investors should be in the portfolio of BBCA & BBTN shares with a risk level (σ) of 0.077107 with a return rate (R_i) of 0.207096.

The following table presents return and standard deviation for investment weight of 50% : 50% is as follows :

Table 5. Return and Standard Deviation Investment Weight 50% : 50 %

No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ	No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ	No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ
1	ADRO & AKRA	0,402047	0,272058	36	ASII & TLKM	0,040759	0,089230	71	GGRM & INDF	0,031205	0,098784
2	ADRO & ASII	0,381123	0,251134	37	ASII & UNTR	0,047931	0,082058	72	GGRM & MNCN	0,031892	0,098097
3	ADRO & BBCA	0,485250	0,355261	38	ASII & UNVR	0,039533	0,090455	73	GGRM & PTBA	0,068626	0,061363
4	ADRO & BBNI	0,428609	0,298620	39	ASII & WSKT	0,019695	0,110293	74	GGRM & TLKM	0,039544	0,090444
5	ADRO & BBTN	0,480423	0,350434	40	BBCA & BBNI	0,156248	0,026259	75	GGRM & UNTR	0,046717	0,083272
6	ADRO & GGRM	0,379909	0,249920	41	BBCA & BBTN	0,208061	0,078073	76	GGRM & UNVR	0,038319	0,091670
7	ADRO & INCO	0,423327	0,293339	42	BBCA & GGRM	0,107547	0,022441	77	GGRM & WSKT	0,018481	0,111508
8	ADRO & INDF	0,408907	0,278919	43	BBCA & INCO	0,150966	0,020977	78	INCO & INDF	0,074624	0,055365
9	ADRO & MNCN	0,409594	0,279605	44	BBCA & INDF	0,136546	0,006557	79	INCO & MNCN	0,075310	0,054678
10	ADRO & PTBA	0,446328	0,316339	45	BBCA & MNCN	0,137233	0,007244	80	INCO & PTBA	0,112044	0,017944
11	ADRO & TLKM	0,417247	0,287258	46	BBCA & PTBA	0,173967	0,043978	81	INCO & TLKM	0,082963	0,047025
12	ADRO & UNTR	0,424419	0,294430	47	BBCA & TLKM	0,144885	0,014897	82	INCO & UNTR	0,090135	0,039853
13	ADRO & UNVR	0,416021	0,286032	48	BBCA & UNTR	0,152058	0,022069	83	INCO & UNVR	0,081738	0,048251
14	ADRO & WSKT	0,396183	0,266194	49	BBCA & UNVR	0,143660	0,013671	84	INCO & WSKT	0,061900	0,068089
15	AKRA &	0,025559	0,104430	50	BBCA &	0,123822	0,006167	85	INDF &	0,060890	0,069098

	ASII				WSKT				MNCN		
16	AKRA & BBCA	0,129685	0,000303	51	BBNI & BBTN	0,151421	0,021432	86	INDF & PTBA	0,097624	0,032364
17	AKRA & BBNI	0,073045	0,056944	52	BBNI & GGRM	0,050907	0,079082	87	INDF & TLKM	0,068543	0,061445
18	AKRA & BBTN	0,124858	0,005130	53	BBNI & INCO	0,094326	0,035663	88	INDF & UNTR	0,075715	0,054273
19	AKRA & GGRM	0,024344	0,105644	54	BBNI & INDF	0,079906	0,050083	89	INDF & UNVR	0,067318	0,062671
20	AKRA & INCO	0,067763	0,062226	55	BBNI & MNCN	0,080592	0,049397	90	INDF & WSKT	0,047480	0,082509
21	AKRA & INDF	0,053343	0,076646	56	BBNI & PTBA	0,117326	0,012663	91	MNCN & PTBA	0,098311	0,031678
22	AKRA & MNCN	0,054030	0,075959	57	BBNI & TLKM	0,088245	0,041744	92	MNCN & TLKM	0,069230	0,060759
23	AKRA & PTBA	0,090764	0,039225	58	BBNI & UNTR	0,095417	0,034572	93	MNCN & UNTR	0,076402	0,053587
24	AKRA & TLKM	0,061682	0,068306	59	BBNI & UNVR	0,087019	0,042969	94	MNCN & UNVR	0,068004	0,061985
25	AKRA & UNTR	0,068855	0,061134	60	BBNI & WSKT	0,067181	0,062807	95	MNCN & WSKT	0,048166	0,081823
26	AKRA & UNVR	0,060457	0,069532	61	BBTN & GGRM	0,102720	0,027268	96	PTBA & TLKM	0,105964	0,024025
27	AKRA & WSKT	0,040619	0,089370	62	BBTN & INCO	0,146139	0,016151	97	PTBA & UNTR	0,113136	0,016853
28	ASII & BBCA	0,108762	0,021227	63	BBTN & INDF	0,131719	0,001731	98	PTBA & UNVR	0,104738	0,025251
29	ASII & BBNI	0,052121	0,077867	64	BBTN & MNCN	0,132406	0,002417	99	PTBA & WSKT	0,084900	0,045089
30	ASII & BBTN	0,103935	0,026054	65	BBTN & PTBA	0,169140	0,039151	100	TLKM & UNTR	0,084055	0,045934
31	ASII & GGRM	0,003421	0,126568	66	BBTN & TLKM	0,140058	0,010070	101	TLKM & UNVR	0,075657	0,054332
32	ASII & INCO	0,046840	0,083149	67	BBTN & UNTR	0,147231	0,017242	102	TLKM & WSKT	0,055819	0,074170
33	ASII & INDF	0,032420	0,097569	68	BBTN & UNVR	0,138833	0,008844	103	UNTR & UNVR	0,082829	0,047160
34	ASII & MNCN	0,033106	0,096883	69	BBTN & WSKT	0,118995	0,010994	104	UNTR & WSKT	0,062991	0,066998
35	ASII & PTBA	0,069840	0,060149	70	GGRM & INCO	0,045625	0,084364	105	UNVR & WSKT	0,054593	0,075395

Source : Processed Data, 2020

From Table 5 can be described the expected return chart and stock portfolio risk as follows:

Source : Processed Data, 2020

Figure 2. Expected return and Risk Portfolio stock Investment Weight 50 % : 50 %

Based on Table 5 and Figure 2 it can be determined that with an investment weight of 50% : 50 % that the right stock portfolio investment for the profile of aggressive investors is in the portfolio of ADRO & BBCA shares with a risk level (σ) of 0.355261 with a return rate (R_i) of 0.485250. Furthermore, the profile of conservative investors is in the portfolio of AKRA & BBCA shares with a risk level (σ) of 0.000303 with a return rate (R_i) of 0.129685. As for the profile of moderate investors should be in the portfolio of BBCA & BBTN shares with a risk level (σ) of 0.078073 with a return rate (R_i) of 0.208061.

The following table presents return and standard deviation for investment weight of 60% : 40% is as follows:

Table 6. Return and Standard Deviation Investment Weight 60% : 40 %

No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ	No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ	No	Portfolio Name	Ri	σ
1	ADRO & AKRA	0,473159	0,343171	36	ASII & TLKM	0,033534	0,096454	71	GGRM & INDF	0,025405	0,104583
2	ADRO & ASII	0,456421	0,326432	37	ASII & UNTR	0,039272	0,090717	72	GGRM & MNCN	0,025954	0,104034
3	ADRO & BBCA	0,539722	0,409733	38	ASII & UNVR	0,032554	0,097435	73	GGRM & PTBA	0,055342	0,074647
4	ADRO & BBNI	0,494409	0,364421	39	ASII & WSKT	0,016683	0,113305	74	GGRM & TLKM	0,032077	0,097912
5	ADRO & BBTN	0,535860	0,405872	40	BBCA & BBNI	0,167576	0,037587	75	GGRM & UNTR	0,037814	0,092174
6	ADRO & GGRM	0,455449	0,325460	41	BBCA & BBTN	0,209027	0,079038	76	GGRM & UNVR	0,031096	0,098892
7	ADRO & INCO	0,490184	0,360195	42	BBCA & GGRM	0,128615	0,001373	77	GGRM & WSKT	0,015226	0,114763
8	ADRO & INDF	0,478648	0,348659	43	BBCA & INCO	0,163351	0,033362	78	INCO & INDF	0,077508	0,052481
9	ADRO & MNCN	0,479197	0,349209	44	BBCA & INDF	0,151815	0,021826	79	INCO & MNCN	0,078057	0,051932
10	ADRO & PTBA	0,508584	0,378596	45	BBCA & MNCN	0,152364	0,022375	80	INCO & PTBA	0,107444	0,022544
11	ADRO & TLKM	0,485319	0,355331	46	BBCA & PTBA	0,181751	0,051762	81	INCO & TLKM	0,084179	0,045809
12	ADRO & UNTR	0,491057	0,361069	47	BBCA & TLKM	0,158486	0,028497	82	INCO & UNTR	0,089917	0,040072
13	ADRO & UNVR	0,484339	0,354350	48	BBCA & UNTR	0,164224	0,034235	83	INCO & UNVR	0,083199	0,046790
14	ADRO &	0,468469	0,338480	49	BBCA &	0,157505	0,027517	84	INCO &	0,067329	0,062660

	WSKT				UNVR				WSKT		
15	AKRA & ASII	0,029744	0,100245	50	BBCA & WSKT	0,141635	0,011646	85	INDF & MNCN	0,060753	0,069236
16	AKRA & BBCA	0,113045	0,016944	51	BBNI & BBTN	0,141058	0,011070	86	INDF & PTBA	0,090140	0,039848
17	AKRA & BBNI	0,067732	0,062256	52	BBNI & GGRM	0,060647	0,069342	87	INDF & TLKM	0,066875	0,063113
18	AKRA & BBTN	0,109183	0,020806	53	BBNI & INCO	0,095382	0,034607	88	INDF & UNTR	0,072613	0,057376
19	AKRA & GGRM	0,028772	0,101217	54	BBNI & INDF	0,083846	0,046143	89	INDF & UNVR	0,065895	0,064094
20	AKRA & INCO	0,063507	0,066482	55	BBNI & MNCN	0,084395	0,045594	90	INDF & WSKT	0,050025	0,079964
21	AKRA & INDF	0,051971	0,078018	56	BBNI & PTBA	0,113782	0,016206	91	MNCN & PTBA	0,090964	0,039025
22	AKRA & MNCN	0,052520	0,077469	57	BBNI & TLKM	0,090517	0,039471	92	MNCN & TLKM	0,067699	0,062290
23	AKRA & PTBA	0,081907	0,048081	58	BBNI & UNTR	0,096255	0,033734	93	MNCN & UNTR	0,073437	0,056552
24	AKRA & TLKM	0,058642	0,071346	59	BBNI & UNVR	0,089537	0,040452	94	MNCN & UNVR	0,066719	0,063270
25	AKRA & UNTR	0,064380	0,065609	60	BBNI & WSKT	0,073667	0,056322	95	MNCN & WSKT	0,050848	0,079140
26	AKRA & UNVR	0,057662	0,072327	61	BBTN & GGRM	0,122823	0,007165	96	PTBA & TLKM	0,111780	0,018209
27	AKRA & WSKT	0,041792	0,088197	62	BBTN & INCO	0,157558	0,027570	97	PTBA & UNTR	0,117518	0,012471
28	ASII & BBCA	0,087937	0,042052	63	BBTN & INDF	0,146022	0,016034	98	PTBA & UNVR	0,110799	0,019189
29	ASII & BBNI	0,042624	0,087364	64	BBTN & MNCN	0,146571	0,016583	99	PTBA & WSKT	0,094929	0,035060
30	ASII & BBTN	0,084075	0,045914	65	BBTN & PTBA	0,175959	0,045970	100	TLKM & UNTR	0,082620	0,047369
31	ASII & GGRM	0,003664	0,126325	66	BBTN & TLKM	0,152694	0,022705	101	TLKM & UNVR	0,075902	0,054087
32	ASII & INCO	0,038399	0,091590	67	BBTN & UNTR	0,158431	0,028443	102	TLKM & WSKT	0,060032	0,069957
33	ASII & INDF	0,026863	0,103126	68	BBTN & UNVR	0,151713	0,021724	103	UNTR & UNVR	0,084509	0,045480
34	ASII & MNCN	0,027412	0,102577	69	BBTN & WSKT	0,135843	0,005854	104	UNTR & WSKT	0,068638	0,061350
35	ASII & PTBA	0,056799	0,073189	70	GGRM & INCO	0,036941	0,093047	105	UNVR & WSKT	0,058561	0,071428

Source : Processed Data, 2020

From Table 6 can be described the expected return chart and stock portfolio risk as follows:

Source : Processed Data, 2020

Figure 3. Expected return and Risk Portfolio stock Investment Weight 60 % : 40 %

Based on Table 6 and Figure 3, it can be determined that with an investment weight of 60% : 40 % that the right stock portfolio investment for the profile of aggressive investors is in the portfolio of ADRO & BBCA shares with a risk level (σ) of 0.409733 with a return rate (Ri) of 0.539722. Furthermore, the profile of conservative investors is in the BBCA & GGRM stock portfolio with a risk level (σ) of 0.01373 with a return rate (Ri) of 0.128615. As for the profile of moderate investors should be in the portfolio of BBCA & BBTN shares with a risk level (σ) of 0.079038 with a return rate (Ri) of 0.209027.

Stock portfolios formed as a form of investment diversification are proven to help reduce investment risk. The results of this study showed that the portfolio produces a maximum level of return with a certain level of risk that is in accordance with investor expectations. This shows that through the formation of an optimal portfolio using the Markowitz model can provide portfolio combinations that can minimize risk.

V. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, shares in LQ Index 45 companies for the period 2015–2019 formed an optimal portfolio based on Markowitz's model of 150 stock portfolios. By selecting the portfolio, investors can diversify their shares by selecting several stocks that will be included in the portfolio. Diversification in this research was carried out by weighting by 40% : 60%, 50% : 50% and 60% : 40%. From the overall weighting obtained the results of a portfolio of shares 40% ADRO & 60% BBCA, 50% ADRO & 50% BBCA and 60% ADRO & 40% BBCA are optimal portfolios for aggressive investor profiles, furthermore 40% BBCA stock portfolio & 60% UNVR, 50% AKRA & 50% BBCA, 60% BBCA & 40% GGRM are optimal portfolios for conservative investor profiles. While the stock portfolio of 40% BBCA & 60% BBTN, 50% BBCA & 50% BBTN and 60% BBCA & 40% BBTN is the optimal portfolio for the profile of moderate investors.

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